

Effect of Temperature, Ionic Strength and Dielectric Constant on Dissociation Constants of some Carboxyalkyl Substituted Thioureas

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Acid dissociation constants of some carboxyalkyl substituted thioureas have been determined potentiometrically in aqueous ethanol (75%, v/v) at different ionic strengths and thermodynamic dissociation constants have been calculated from these data. Dissociation constants at fixed ionic strength (0.1 mol dm⁻³) over the temperature range 10 - 50° and in different solvent-water systems have been determined. The thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated and the effect of dielectric constants on dissociation constant has been discussed.

DISSOCIATION constants of some heterocyclic thioureas, like substituted pyridyl-, thiazolyl- and pyrimidyl-thiourea have been studied¹. The acid-base equilibria of some *N*-substituted-*N'*-(carboxyalkyl)thioureas do not appear to have been studied so far. It was therefore thought of interest to synthesise some carboxyalkyl substituted thioureas and determine their dissociation constants and also study the effect of ionic strength, temperature and solvent on dissociation constant of these compounds.

Experimental

All chemicals were of G.R. grade (E. Merck or Sarabhai M). The following compounds were synthesised: *N*-ethyl- (1), *N*-benzyl- (2) and *N*-*p*-tolyl-*N'*-(carboxymethyl)thiourea (3); *N*-ethyl- (4), *N*-benzyl- (5) and *N*-*p*-tolyl-*N'*-(carboxyethyl)thiourea (6); *N*-ethyl- (7), *N*-benzyl- (8) and *N*-*p*-tolyl-*N'*-(1-carboxy, 2-phenylethyl)thiourea (9); *N*-ethyl- (10), *N*-benzyl- (11) and *N*-*p*-tolyl-*N'*-(1-carboxy, 2-hydroxypropyl)thiourea (12); *N*-ethyl- (13), *N*-benzyl- (14) and *N*-*p*-tolyl-*N'*-(1,2-dicarboxyethyl)thiourea (15) by condensing substituted amino acids (glycine, alanine, β -phenylalanine, threonine and aspartic acid) with ethyl, benzyl and *p*-tolyl

isothiocyanates (Table 1). Their structures have been established on the basis of elemental analysis and spectral studies. Ethanol, methanol, dioxane and acetonitrile were purified² and carbonate-free KOH was prepared³. NaClO₄·2H₂O (Riedel) was used for maintaining the ionic strength.

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL DATA OF *N*-ARYL(ALKYL)-*N'*-(SUBSTITUTED-CARBOXYALKYL)THIOUREAS

Compd. no.	R	R ₁	Mol. formula
1	H	C ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S
2	H	CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S
3	H	C ₆ H ₄ ·(CH ₃ - <i>p</i>)	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S
4	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S
5	CH ₃	CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S
6	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃ - <i>p</i>)	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ S
7	CH ₂ ·C ₆ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S
8	CH ₂ ·C ₆ H ₅	CH ₂ ·C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ S
9	CH ₂ ·C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃ - <i>p</i>)	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S
10	CH(OH)·CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	C ₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S
11	CH(OH)·CH ₃	CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S
12	CH(OH)·CH ₃	C ₆ H ₄ ·(CH ₃ - <i>p</i>)	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S
13	CH ₂ ·COOH	C ₂ H ₅	C ₇ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S
14	CH ₂ ·COOH	CH ₂ ·C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S
15	CH ₂ ·COOH	C ₆ H ₄ ·(CH ₃ - <i>p</i>)	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ S

Direct pH titration method⁴ was employed to determine the dissociation constant of the compounds. The pH measurements were made on a NIG 333 digital pH meter using a glass-calomel electrode assembly. The pH meter was calibrated with standard buffers before each titrations to

ensure reproducibility. Necessary corrections in pH for different solvent systems were made⁴. The solution was maintained free of carbon dioxide by passing CO₂-free nitrogen which had previously been passed through a presaturator containing 0.1 M KCl⁵. Dissociation constant of COOH group was determined following the method of Chattopadhyay and Lahiri⁶ in which a known concentration of the compound was neutralised to different extents with perchloric acid and the hydrogen ion concentration measured. For the determination of dissociation constants of amino group, hydroxy group and thiol group, the process was the same, only that perchloric acid was replaced by sodium hydroxide³. The pK values were calculated by using equation (1),

$$pK = pH + \log_{10} \frac{[HA] - [OH^-]}{[A^-] + [OH^-]} + F \quad (1)$$

where the terms within the brackets refer to the stoichiometric concentrations of the appropriate species and *F* is the activity correction term⁷. The values of pK_{II} in each case were calculated by picking up a point on the titration curve where less than one mole of alkali per mole of the ligand had been added. The values of pK_{III} and pK_{IV} were calculated in the region between one and two equivalent of base and two and three equivalent of base respectively. Thermodynamic dissociation constants (pK_a^T) of these compounds were obtained by determining the dissociation constants at 30.0 ± 0. ° and at different ionic strengths (*μ*), viz. 0.02, 0.05, 0.10, 0.15 and 0.20 mol dm⁻³ and extrapolating the plot of pK vs ionic strength

For the determination of thermodynamic parameters, the studies were carried out at 10, 20, 40 and 50° and at a fixed ionic strength (0.1 mol dm⁻³). The thermodynamic parameters such as free energy change (ΔG), enthalpy change (ΔH) and entropy change (ΔS) were evaluated. In order to study the effect of dielectric constant on the dissociation constants of these substituted thioureas, the studies were carried out in different solvent-water systems (75 : 25, v/v), viz ethanol-water, methanol-water, dioxane-water and acetonitrile-water at fixed temperature 30.0 ± 0.1° and fixed ionic strength (0.1 mol dm⁻³).

Results and Discussion

Compounds 1–9 have three dissociation constants (Table 2). The pK_I, pK_{II} and pK_{III} values are due to the dissociation of carboxylic group, NH₂⁺ group (NH₂⁺ group is formed in the zwitterion structure of these substituted thioureas) and thiol group which is formed by the proton shift from the adjacent N to the thiocarbonyl group respectively. Compounds 10–15 have four dissociation

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF THE THIOUREAS IN 75% (v/v) ETHANOL-WATER AT 30.0 ± 0.1°

Compd. no.	pK _I ^T	pK _{II} ^T	pK _{III} ^T	pK _{IV} ^T
1	4.16	10.36	11.46	—
2	4.01	10.23	11.31	—
3	3.79	10.04	11.10	—
4	4.37	10.53	11.70	—
5	4.17	10.36	11.53	—
6	3.98	10.24	11.31	—
7	4.22	10.41	11.56	—
8	4.05	10.21	11.41	—
9	3.82	10.10	11.23	—
10	4.57	7.89	10.87	12.01
11	4.47	7.73	10.75	11.86
12	4.25	7.57	10.56	11.67
13	3.97	5.80	10.67	11.85
14	3.85	5.65	10.56	11.73
15	3.61	5.44	10.29	11.50

constants. The pK_I, pK_{II}, pK_{III} and pK_{IV} of these compounds are due to the dissociation of carboxylic, NH₂⁺, OH, and thiol groups. In compounds 13–15, the pK_I and pK_{II} are due to the dissociation of two carboxylic groups. The pK_{III} is due to the dissociation of NH₂⁺ group and pK_{IV} due to the dissociation of thiol group.

From the results obtained at different ionic strengths, it is observed that dissociation constants of these heterocyclic substituted thioureas decrease with increase in ionic strength from 0.02 to 0.20 M.

An examination of thermodynamic dissociation constants (Table 2) indicate that pK_I^T of these compounds are in the range 3.61–4.57, and this may be due to dissociation of carboxylic group. The pK_{II}^T value of 1–9 and pK_{III}^T value of 13–15 are due to the dissociation of NH₂⁺ group and the value lies in the range 10.04–10.67 and for 10–12, the value lies in the range 7.57–7.89. For compounds 13–15, the pK_{II}^T values are in the range 5.44–5.80 which is due to the dissociation of second carboxylic group. Amongst all the compounds, tolyl substituted compounds are strong and ethyl substituted compounds are weak acids; the other compounds have intermediate pK value. The trend in pK values can be understood by the electron donor-acceptor properties of alkyl/aryl group. Assuming tolyl group to be an acceptor of electron, it facilitates the release of proton by withdrawing electrons from the acidic group. The other substituent, i.e ethyl and benzyl act basically as electron donors. Thus the release of proton is more difficult in these cases and hence the higher

TABLE 3 - VALUES OF THE PARAMETERS CALCULATED FROM THE HARNED'S EQUATION FOR THE THIOUREAS

Compd. no.	pK _{mI}	pK _{mII}	pK _{mIII}	pK _{mIV}	θ _I °C	θ _{II} °C	θ _{III} °C	θ _{IV} °C	ΔH (average) (kJ mol ⁻¹)			
									ΔH _I	ΔH _{II}	ΔH _{III}	ΔH _{IV}
1	2.42	8.43	9.44	-	195.0	207.5	212.5	-	28.86	31.05	31.95	-
2	2.21	8.20	9.35	-	197.5	212.5	210.5	-	29.30	31.95	31.51	-
3	2.45	8.03	9.02	-	172.5	210.0	215.0	-	24.90	31.51	32.39	-
4	2.59	8.44	9.51	-	197.5	217.5	220.0	-	29.30	32.83	33.27	-
5	2.18	8.21	9.36	-	210.0	230.0	220.0	-	31.51	33.27	33.27	-
6	1.91	8.11	9.05	-	215.0	217.5	225.0	-	32.39	32.83	34.16	-
7	2.36	8.35	9.20	-	202.5	215.0	230.0	-	30.19	32.39	35.04	-
8	2.23	8.10	9.14	-	200.0	217.5	215.0	-	29.75	32.83	34.16	-
9	2.07	7.98	8.83	-	197.5	217.5	230.0	-	29.30	32.83	35.04	-
10	2.49	5.96	8.63	9.51	215.0	207.5	222.5	235.0	32.39	31.05	33.71	35.92
11	2.52	5.66	8.44	9.37	207.5	215.0	215.0	235.0	31.05	32.39	34.16	35.92
12	2.30	5.48	8.30	9.22	207.5	215.0	222.5	232.5	31.05	32.39	33.71	35.48
13	2.22	3.97	8.60	9.70	197.5	202.5	215.0	220.0	29.30	30.19	32.39	33.27
14	1.91	3.72	8.47	9.51	207.5	207.5	215.0	222.5	31.05	31.05	32.39	33.71
15	1.74	3.49	8.22	9.23	205.0	207.5	215.0	225.0	30.63	31.05	32.39	34.16

pK_a^T values (weaker acids). The pK values of ethyl and benzyl substituted thioureas correlate well with the electron donor properties of these groups. An identical explanation corresponds to the increasing trend in pK_{mI}^T values of compounds 1-9 and pK_{mIV}^T values of compounds 10-15 which is due to the dissociation of thiol group. The pK_{mIII}^T values of compounds 10-12 are higher because OH group at C₂ is stabilised because of hydrogen bonding with COO⁻ group.

Results of dissociation constant at different temperatures reveal that the increase in temperature leads to a decrease in pK values. This is normally observed for more acids in the range studied 10-50°. The values of ΔG are positive, indicating that the reaction is not spontaneous. The positive values of ΔH indicate that the dissociation is an endothermic process. The values of ΔS are negative showing a greater amount of order in the ionised species as compared to the undissociated acids.

The minimum pK_a (pK_m) values at definite temperature (θ) were calculated by using the Harned equation,

$$pK_a - pK_m = C(t - \theta)^2 \quad (2)$$

or on rearrangement,

$$pK_a - Ct^2 = pK_m + C\theta^2 - 2C\theta t \quad (3)$$

where pK_a = -log K_a at temperature t, pK_m is minimum pK_a value at θ and C a constant of the order 5 × 10⁻² K⁻².

The plots of pK_I-Ct², pK_{II}-Ct², pK_{III}-Ct² and pK_{IV}-Ct² vs t for these compounds are found to be linear. From these plots, the values of θ_I, θ_{II}, θ_{III}, θ_{IV}, pK_{mI}, pK_{mII}, pK_{mIII} and pK_{mIV} have been calculated (Table 3). In these compounds, the θ_I values (θ values of pK_I) are in the order, 10=6>5>14=12=11>15>7>8>3=9=4=2>1>3. This trend can not be explained easily because of the higher energies of the molecule around the temperature θ, the normal electronic and steric consideration may not be valid. The plots of pK_I, pK_{II}, pK_{III} and pK_{IV} vs t are also linear in the range studied. The ΔH value was obtained from the value of θ and t by using equation (4).

$$\Delta H = -2.303 \times 10^{-4} RT^2 (t - \theta) \quad (4)$$

as suggested by Harned *et al.*⁹. The ΔH values at various temperature thus obtained compare favourably with those obtained from the pK_I versus 1/T plots supporting Harned's assumption that pK_I-pK_{mI} or pK_{II}-pK_{mII} or pK_{III}-pK_{mIII} or pK_{IV}-pK_{mIV} is a parabolic function of temperature at least to a first approximation.

Dissociation constants of these carboxyalkyl substituted thioureas in different solvents of varying dielectric constant, viz. dioxane-water, ethanol-water, methanol-water and acetonitrile-water at fixed ionic strength (0.10M) and at 30.0 ± 0.1° are recorded in Table 4. The choice of mixed solvent was due to the insolubility of these compounds in aqueous media and in other non-polar solvents. The results indicate that as the dielectric constant decreases, the dissociation constant

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF SOLVENTS ON pK VALUES OF THE THIOUREAS AT 30.0 ± 0.1° (IONIC STRENGTH 0.10 mol dm⁻³)

Compd. no.	Dissociation constant	Solvent-water (75 : 25, v/v)*			
		Dioxane-water (14 2)	Ethanol-water (38 0)	Methanol-water (45 0)	Acetonitrile-water (-)
1	pK _I	4.66	3.81	3.41	3.10
	pK _{II}	10.85	10.05	9.60	9.30
	pK _{III}	11.84	11.14	10.60	10.28
2	pK _I	4.46	3.64	3.24	2.92
	pK _{II}	10.66	9.91	9.45	9.12
	pK _{III}	11.68	11.00	10.45	10.12
3	pK _I	4.28	3.45	3.07	2.76
	pK _{II}	10.45	9.70	9.24	8.92
	pK _{III}	11.48	10.78	10.25	9.90
4	pK _I	4.93	4.03	3.65	3.33
	pK _{II}	11.00	10.24	9.78	9.45
	pK _{III}	12.01	11.36	10.81	10.46
5	pK _I	4.72	3.84	3.44	3.11
	pK _{II}	10.78	10.04	9.58	9.25
	pK _{III}	11.84	11.20	10.65	10.30
6	pK _I	4.51	3.66	3.25	2.93
	pK _{II}	10.67	9.92	9.47	9.13
	pK _{III}	11.65	11.00	10.45	13.11
7	pK _I	4.76	3.88	3.49	3.16
	pK _{II}	10.84	10.10	9.62	9.30
	pK _{III}	11.91	11.23	10.68	10.36
8	pK _I	4.55	3.70	3.30	2.98
	pK _{II}	10.71	9.90	9.49	9.16
	pK _{III}	11.73	11.08	10.54	10.21
9	pK _I	4.35	3.51	3.12	2.80
	pK _{II}	10.54	9.78	9.32	9.00
	pK _{III}	11.52	10.88	10.32	10.00
10	pK _I	5.05	4.23	3.83	3.50
	pK _{II}	8.36	7.56	7.14	6.80
	pK _{III}	11.25	10.52	10.05	9.70
	pK _{IV}	12.26	11.65	11.10	10.75
11	pK _I	4.92	4.12	3.72	3.40
	pK _{II}	8.20	7.40	6.98	6.64
	pK _{III}	11.11	10.38	9.92	9.57
	pK _{IV}	12.12	11.51	10.94	10.60
12	pK _I	4.72	3.90	3.50	3.18
	pK _{II}	8.00	7.22	6.80	6.45
	pK _{III}	10.95	10.20	9.73	9.40
	pK _{IV}	11.92	11.30	10.75	10.40
13	pK _I	4.55	3.65	3.26	2.95
	pK _{II}	6.26	5.48	5.03	4.70
	pK _{III}	11.05	10.35	9.90	9.58
	pK _{IV}	12.20	11.54	11.00	10.68
14	pK _I	4.40	3.52	3.12	2.80
	pK _{II}	6.12	5.33	4.88	4.54
	pK _{III}	10.92	10.22	9.76	9.40
	pK _{IV}	12.04	11.40	10.85	10.50
15	pK _I	4.20	3.30	2.90	2.60
	pK _{II}	5.90	5.10	4.65	4.30
	pK _{III}	10.70	9.97	9.50	9.15
	pK _{IV}	11.80	11.17	10.62	10.30

*Figures in parenthesis are dielectric constants of solvent-water system.

decreases. It can be observed (Table 4) that as the dielectric constant of the solvent increases, pK_a decreases showing high acidity¹⁰.

Among the solvents, ethanol and methanol are protic in character and can make available a proton for sharing with other atoms or molecules. The solvents selected for the present studies are acidic in character. The effect of dielectric constant and that of acidic character of solvents on dissociation constant is prominent. Water molecules are known to solvate hydrogen ions. From Table 4, it can be seen that all these compounds are stronger acids in acetonitrile-water media than in dioxane-water media, as acetonitrile can easily accept electrons from the anion by forming a complex and thereby stabilises the anion.

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